

DEVELOPMENT OF MODERN LAND MANAGEMENT ACTIVITIES AND PRESSING TASKS IN CREATING A COMPREHENSIVE CADASTRE SYSTEM

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the economic regulation of land management activities and provides general information about the effective and rational use of land resources, particularly agricultural lands. Recommendations are presented for the development of modern land management practices and the establishment of a comprehensive cadastral system.*

Keywords: *geodesy, cartography, cadaster, land management, land registration, commercial buildings, forest fund, reserve lands.*

Introduction: Land management and cadastral registration, as social phenomena, date back to the early days of human agricultural activities. As society progressed, the concept of "land management" (the process of defining land ownership rights and legally registering land rights) evolved into the broader term "land use planning" (activities related to the economic regulation of land plots). With land becoming a property object, the significance of land management and cadaster has substantially increased.

Land management and cadastral systems play a crucial role in ensuring the efficient and rational use of the state's land resources, particularly agricultural lands. These systems also help in maintaining records of land and other real estate properties, developing the real estate market, generating budget revenues from real estate usage, securing property rights, enabling fair taxation, and ensuring just income distribution among the population.

Land management and cadaster have simultaneously evolved into a set of actions encompassing legal, technical, organizational-economic, and financial aspects.

The primary objective of land management is to organize territories rationally, establish order through optimal placement, and efficiently manage land. Land governance must be based on principles of self-sufficiency, commercial benefit, and effectiveness.

Maintaining a state real estate cadaster based on national land cadaster data is aimed at providing the government and society with crucial legal information. This primarily concerns

guaranteeing property rights, supporting the tax system, securing mortgage loans, developing land transactions, enforcing government oversight, resolving land disputes, implementing land reforms, fostering regional development, and ensuring environmental protection.

During the land reform process in the Republic of Uzbekistan, fundamental changes have occurred in land relations, significantly influencing land status and usage. The state's monopoly over land ownership has been abolished, leading to the emergence of a multi-structured system of land ownership and utilization. Land redistribution, the creation of a land market, and the introduction of land-related fees have also taken place.

Table 1

Information on Land Fund Categories of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Land categories	As of January 1, 2024 (thousand ha)	%
Agricultural land	26132,2	58,21
Land of settlements	226,7	0,51
Land designated for industry, transport, communication, defense, and other purposes	786,9	1,75
Land for environmental protection, health improvement, and recreational purposes	3223,3	7,18
Land of historical and cultural significance	15,0	0,03
Forest fund land	12092,5	26,94
Water fund land	827,3	1,84
Reserve land	1588,5	3,54
Total land	44892,4	100

Currently, more than 42 million landowners exist in Uzbekistan, totaling approximately 112,000 legal entities and individuals. Historically, land management has been the principal mechanism for implementing land reforms.

Since the beginning of land relations reform in Uzbekistan, land management has served as a tool for withdrawing land from state control and privatizing it, restructuring former collective and state farms, redistributing land, and transferring it to new economic entities. These transformations have affected nearly all Uzbek citizens and legal entities. The reform process has included privatizing household plots and land for real estate, granting land shares in agricultural enterprises, circulating land plots in the market, and establishing a redistribution fund.

The geopolitical, socio-economic, and environmental interests of Uzbekistan, along with the state's goal of integrating land and property assets into active economic circulation to accelerate growth, necessitate a significant expansion of land management and territorial planning systems. These systems serve as primary mechanisms for regulating land relations and directing the nation's land resources towards essential economic goals.

Despite the tangible results of the reforms, Uzbekistan's land reform process remains incomplete. Some of the unresolved issues include:

- Development of real estate markets and their infrastructure within land and property relations;
- Ensuring broader access to land resources for the population;

- Eliminating challenges associated with efficiently transferring land to rightful owners;
- Addressing inconsistencies in numerous legal and regulatory documents;
- Determining cadastral land valuation;
- Addressing the lack of land management support for land use, among others.

For these reasons, modernizing land management and creating an advanced cadastral system must be a top priority in the country's political, social, and economic agenda.

Research Methodology. The study employs historical, retrospective, and theoretical-methodological analyses, along with data synthesis and interpretation. Additional research methods include observation, interviews, surveys, content analysis, qualitative evaluation, and expert assessments.

Research Findings. Land management involves studying land conditions and conducting coordinated cartographic, engineering, technical, and inventory-related activities. These processes aim to regulate territorial organization, determine land management boundaries, ensure rational land use, protect land resources, enhance the landscape, and create a favorable land-use environment.

Land resource management in Uzbekistan is regulated by the Land Code, Forestry Code, Urban Planning Code, the Law "On Land Management," and various governmental resolutions and departmental regulations.

Land management and cadaster activities include:

- **Aerial photography** (aerial imaging of land plots);
- **Topographic and geodetic surveys;**
- **Soil science research;**
- **Geobotanical studies.**

These activities involve land mapping, boundary assessments, measurement surveys, and developing proposals for rational land use. They facilitate the collection of quantitative and qualitative data on land areas.

The territories of Uzbekistan's administrative divisions, municipal districts, and other land management objects—such as state-owned lands—are systematically assessed to collect and analyze data on land areas' quantitative and qualitative characteristics.

To ensure data reliability, technical and technological standards are established for the certification of measurement tools used in land management and cadaster assessments. Based on the conducted surveys, various land management documents—such as diagrams, land area plans, and land-use projects—are developed.

For each land management object, a compiled portfolio of land management documentation is created. Land plans detail total land area, the placement of various facilities, engineering infrastructure, and natural objects. These plans also include restrictions and encumbrances on land use, such as servitude rights.

The presence of land plans is mandatory for land transactions, including purchasing, selling, and other legal agreements.

Regional land management focuses on studying land conditions, organizing their rational use, defining administrative-territorial boundaries, and assessing land management objects. It plays a crucial role in cases of boundary changes, identifying degraded lands, implementing land conservation measures, and redistributing land shares.

Additionally, regional land management includes:

- Defining and modifying urban and rural settlement boundaries;
- Zoning urban territories;
- Establishing national parks and protected areas;
- Designating zones with special land-use regimes for enterprises and institutions.

Land management in farming enterprises aims to optimize the use of already allocated agricultural land. It also facilitates the organization of lands used by local communities. In practice, this involves developing or approving plans for agricultural lands, pasturelands, residential and industrial construction sites, and transport infrastructure.

Land management in farming enterprises is carried out upon the request of landowners who have been allocated specific land plots.

In conclusion, large-scale land management work remains to be conducted in Uzbekistan's administrative divisions, municipal districts, and other state-managed territories. This includes defining boundaries, conducting land inventories, integrating cadaster records, and implementing territorial planning strategies to promote rational land use and environmental protection.

Furthermore, individual landowners and users must take the initiative in funding land management activities within their territories to ensure effective and sustainable land use.

Conclusion. The implementation of land management processes allows for achieving the following outcomes:

- Clearly defining the boundaries of real estate objects and registering them in the cadastral registry, thereby strengthening and guaranteeing the rights of landowners and land users;
- Enhancing the efficiency of land and real estate use through investment-based land management projects, contributing to the development of national and regional economies and stimulating investment activities in the real estate market;
- Ensuring the rational use and protection of land, as well as implementing effective land resource management through the optimal placement of capital construction, industrial, and social infrastructure facilities;
- Systematically updating land cadaster and state monitoring data, improving the forms and methods of state land control;
- Defining the boundaries of cities and other administrative-territorial structures, as well as areas with special legal and environmental regimes, thereby strengthening local self-governance and differentiating the legal regimes of land use;
- Fully implementing agricultural land reforms by eliminating anonymity in the use of land shares within fertile land areas and non-agricultural lands, ensuring the proper accounting of land holdings in agricultural enterprises;
- Regulating land allocation, withdrawal, and reclassification based on territorial planning documents, zoning regulations, and designated land use types, ensuring social justice in land redistribution while balancing state, public, and private interests;
- Developing a well-regulated land market, fostering mortgage lending, and creating conditions for the circulation of land plots;
- Identifying new lands for agricultural and other economic development.

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